

Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe

CURE provides the means to cope with the Earth Observation data in the domain of sustainable and resilient urbanization, by combining products of different Copernicus Core Services. In this context, CURE develops a system, consisting of individual cross-cutting applications for climate change adaptation/mitigation, energy and economy, as well as healthy cities and social environments.

CURE contributes to the scientific and operational exploitation of the existing and upcoming European space infrastructure, by providing novel ideas on how Copernicus can promote valuable information for urban resilience.

 <http://cure-copernicus.eu>

 CURE - Copernicus for Urban Resilience in Europe

 @H2020Cure

 CURE H2020 Project

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Copernicus

is the European Union's Earth Observation Programme, looking at our planet and its environment for the ultimate benefit of all European citizens. CURE deploys its Core Services and develops cross-cutting applications for cities.

Urban

areas are exceptionally vulnerable to climate change and their vulnerability is increasing over time. City administrations are prompted to embed climate change mitigation and adaptation in both urban planning and development.

Resilience

has become an important necessity for cities, in order to properly preserve their functions and to adapt/transform their systems in the face of climate change.

Europe

promotes urban sustainability and resilience, as they are outlined in the New Urban Agenda and the European Green Deal.